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Research and Analysis on Colleges Student View the "Four Regression" of Applied Higher Education Institutions: Take Jiangzhe Higher School as a Case

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Abstract

It has become a common phenomenon in universities that "crazy university, happy universities," which makes it urgent for higher education to "return to common sense, duty, original heart, and dream." Following the general direction of "education reform," this paper proposes the hypothesis that "four regressions" which can affect students' regression criteria on the basis of combing relevant literatures domestically and abroad and verifies its correctness through structural equation. In addition, the user's portrait was used to analyze and conclude the characteristics of college students, and regression analysis was used to explore its causes, so as to make suggestions for educational reform.

Keywords: "Four Regression," Structural Equation, User Profile Analysis, Regression Analysis

1 Introduction

The research on the study of Chinese university students and analysis of college students in the United States point out it is a common phenomenon that it exist problems of low classroom challenges and the light academic burden of college students in China universities. On June 21, 2018, Minister Chen Baosheng delivered an important speech at the Undergraduate Education Work Conference of the New Era National College of Higher Education, "Adhering to the principle of promoting the four-fold return to build a first-class undergraduate education with Chinese characteristics and world-class level." The "four regressions" firstly emphasizes that college students should realize "return to common sense"; the director of the Department of Higher Education, Wu Yan^②, also interprets the new development of higher education reform and development in the speech of "Comprehensively grasping the situation and revitalizing the undergraduate to play the role of the teaching and learning committee fully" . "Four Returns" points out that college students should study hard and return to common sense. In summary, the definition of "four regressions" is defined as returning to common sense,

students should study hard and master the skills for practical service; returning to the duty, teachers should continue and convey spiritual values, and also should concentrate on teaching and educating students; At first glance, colleges and universities should cultivate talents that the society needs and conform to the development of the times; returning to dreams, education must be a dream of building a first-class university and building a first-class discipline.

Domestic similar subjects mainly focus on three aspects of college academics, students' rating system, and university reform. Zhang Liangyue and Guo Suling^[1] believe that local colleges and universities still have problems in the overall development of education, which is still stuck in the development model that satisfies demand, and the insufficiency of connotation development. It should pay attention to the development of specialty and discipline, attach importance to the development of teachers' connotation, and pay attention to improving students' ability development in three aspects. Shang Hongjuan^[2] proposed through the study of first-class undergraduate education in the United States. In the undergraduate study period, American universities aim to provide students with adequate learning opportunities and learning rights, focusing on cultivating students' critical thinking and curiosity, emphasizing students' five core competencies of writing, reading, querying, quantitative analysis, and communication to allow students to "learn how to learn."

Similar topics abroad focus on the evaluation system of higher education quality and the factors that affect the quality of education. The certification of colleges and universities in the United States include the student dimension indicators, which focus on improving the quality of students' training. Pace^[3] and Austin^[4] emphasize the important role of learning input. The former emphasizes the time and effort of learning input, while the latter combines learning input with the external environment to influence the learning output jointly.

Through combing the domestic and foreign literatures, we found that most scholars have reached a consensus on the issue of "current university education needs reform." At the same time, many scholars believe that university education reform has entered the deep water area, and the reform at this stage needs to be led by scholars. At the same time, the government's influence on the issue is reduced. Most scholars only elaborate on the relationship between reform and education, the thinking of reform, and the goal of reform, but they ignore the main role of students in it. However, in order to truly achieve the goal of improving the quality of university education, it is necessary to start from the students and gain an in-depth understanding of the factors that influence the better development of students throughout the education system. However, there are few systematic models in the literature about "factors affecting student development," and fewer literatures elaborate on systematic strategies that influence the return of contemporary college students.

2 Methodology

Overall, this paper takes the undergraduate students in Zhejiang Province as the survey and uses the structural equation to verify the hypothesis that "four regressions" affecting the students' regression criteria. Through cluster analysis and regression analysis, three types of student portraits are formed, and the causes are explored. A total of 472 questionnaires were issued, 448 valid questionnaires, the effective rate was 94.9%, and the reliability coefficient Cronbach's Alpha was 0.815. The reliability was good. There are 200 males and 248 females in the gender distribution. There are 50 key universities, 274 general undergraduate colleges, and 121 independent colleges. The samples have good representativeness and stability.

2.1 Structural equation

In order to verify the "four regressions" which can influence the hypothesis of student regression criteria, and in order to quantitatively explore the strength of the relationship under the assumption, the hypothesis is established, the indicators constructed from the literature review and interviews observed variables, corresponding to the structure " Exogenous latent variables of four regressions and endogenous latent variables affect students' regression criteria, using AMOS 23.0 and solving the model parameters by maximum likelihood estimation method, establishing measurement model and structural model .

The measurement model describes the relationship between the latent variables ξ, η and the observed variables X, Y . Where Y is a vector of endogenous observation variables; X is a vector of exogenous observation variables; η is an endogenous latent variable; ξ is an exogenous latent variable; Λ_Y is an endogenous observation variable on the endogenous latent variable Factor load matrix, which represents the relationship between the endogenous latent variable η and its observed variable Y ; Λ_X is the factor loading matrix of the exogenous observed variable on the exogenous latent variable, which represents the exogenous latent variable ξ and its observed variable X . The relationship between ε and σ is the residual matrix of the measurement equation.

$$Y = \Lambda_Y \eta + \varepsilon$$

$$X = \Lambda_X \xi + \sigma$$

The structural model expresses the relationship between exogenous latent variables and endogenous latent variables and graphically forms a path map. Where B is a matrix of structural coefficients, which represents the interaction between the constituent elements of the endogenous latent variable η ; Γ is a matrix of structural coefficients, which represents the effect of the exogenous latent variable ξ on the endogenous latent variable η ; Difference matrix.

$$\eta = B\eta + \Gamma\xi + \zeta$$

Fig 0-1. The exogenous latent variables of the "four regressions" and the endogenous latent variables that affect the regression of students

Table 0-1. Observed variables corresponding to each latent variable

Latent variable	Observation variable
Return to common sense	Requirements for your own achievements (V1)
	Extracurricular reading (V2)
	Reading breadth (V3)
	Interest in professional course learning (V4)
	Willingness to participate in research/disciplinary competition (V5)
	Academic burden (V6)
Return to the point	Teacher's response to student questions outside the classroom (V7)
	The spirit of the teacher's class (V8)
	Whether teaching combines theory with practice (V9)
	The teacher pays attention to guiding students in the classroom (V10)
Return to the beginning	University culture atmosphere (V11)
	Optional curriculum (V12)
	The Influence of Ideological and Political Education on Personality Molding and the Formation of Three Views (V13)
	The Influence of Ideological and Political Education on Cognitive Understanding of Socialism (V14)
Return to dreams	Teaching equipment (V15)
	Library Facilities (V16)
	School-enterprise alliance (V17)
	Learning Resources (V18)
Regression standard	University overall harvest (V19)
	Professional course mastery (V20)
	Current attention (V21)
	Whether the target is clear (V22)

The model path coefficients are significant ($P < 0.05$). From the results of the correlation fitting index evaluation, the mean squared and square root RMSEA are $0.045 < 0.08$; the CFI of the degree of fitness is $0.918 > 0.9$. The adjusted fitness index AGFI is $0.911 > 0.9$, the indicators have reached the acceptable range, and the model fits well, and the assumption is established.

In the influence of exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables, the path coefficient of "return to common sense" is the largest, 0.84; the path coefficient of "return to dream" is small, only 0.22. Explain that "return to common sense" can have a large positive impact on regression criteria. In the correlation between exogenous latent variables, the correlation coefficient between "returning common sense" and "returning to dream" is relatively high, 0.7, and the two have obvious joint actions, which can be jointly constructed; "returning common sense" is related to "returning the score" The coefficient is second, 0.58, that is, attention should be paid to the interaction between students and teachers.

2.2 Student Portrait

The current heterogeneity of college students is strong. Scientifically summarizing its typical characteristics helps quickly and comprehensively and accurately recognize college students and promotes the precise implementation of the “four regressions” of higher education. In order to construct a representative student portrait, this paper converts the numerical data into discrete values from 1 to 5, achieves dimensionality reduction by principal component analysis to avoid multi-collinearity, and weights the cluster distance with the principal component score as the weight. Clustering.

Table 0-2.2 distance weight analysis table of principal components

ingredient	Extracting the sum of squared loads		
	Total	Percentage of variance	Cumulative %
1	5.023	22.833	22.833
2	1.830	8.316	31.149
3	1.744	7.926	39.075
4	1.356	6.165	45.240
5	1.115	5.069	50.310
6	1.047	4.759	55.068
7	.882	4.009	59.077
8	.811	3.685	62.763
9	.773	3.516	66.278
10	.765	3.477	69.755
11	.742	3.373	73.128
12	.687	3.124	76.252
13	.654	2.972	79.223
14	.627	2.852	82.075
15	.594	2.702	84.777
16	.576	2.617	87.393
17	.547	2.487	89.880
18	.499	2.268	92.148
19	.465	2.112	94.260
20	.447	2.033	96.293
21	.419	1.906	98.199
22	.396	1.801	100.000

It is known from Table 2 that the variance contribution rate of the first 16 principal components is 87%, which is enough to represent the most of the sample information. The 16 principal components are recalculated to

calculate the principal component scores of the sample, and the weighted principal component distance is defined as the weight. The K-means method is used for clustering. Let $F_1, F_2, \dots, F_m (m \leq p)$ be the principal component extracted from the p-dimensional index vector $X = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p)^T$, and $\alpha_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, p)$ is the variance contribution rate of the main component F_k , Let $\beta_k = \alpha_k / \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, p)$ be the main component F_k distance weight. Define the weighted principal component distance between samples I, j as:

$$d_{ij}(q) = \left[\sum_{k=1}^m (\beta_k (F_{ik} - F_{jk}))^q \right]^{1/q}$$

The distance weights of the 16 principal components are as shown in Table 2, which eliminates the collinear overlapping information of the original indicators, and reflects the difference in the content of the primary components including the original indicators. The clustering effect is better.

Table 2-3. distance weight analysis table of principal components

Principal component 1	0.228	Principal component 9	0.035
Principal component 2	0.083	Principal component 10	0.035
Principal component 3	0.079	Principal component 11	0.034
Principal component 4	0.062	Principal component 12	0.031
Principal component 5	0.051	Principal component 13	0.030
Principal component 6	0.048	Principal component 14	0.029
Principal component 7	0.040	Principal component 15	0.027
Principal component 8	0.037	Principal component 16	0.026

In order to better summarize the characteristics of each group, this paper sets the number of clusters to 3 and uses the corresponding analysis to visually show the tendency of the three groups on some observed variables on the double projection map to find the clusters with internal similarity. The students population of the characteristics, the corresponding analysis results are shown in Table 2.

Table 0-4. Summary table of characteristics of the three types of student groups

Category	A	B	C
Gender orientation	Girl	Boy	No inclination
School level	Independent Institute/ General undergraduate	Key university	Independent Institute
Evaluation of the teacher	High	medium	Low/lower
Learning burden	Large/medium	little/high	Medium/smaller
Expertise	Lower/medium	High/higher	Lower/medium
Mastery	Less correspond	correspond	Much correspond

According to the portraits, Class A tends to be female, mostly from independent colleges or general undergraduates. The comprehensive evaluation of teachers is high, the learning burden is medium or large, but the mastery of professional knowledge is at a low level, lacking clear planning and execution. Class B is prone to boys, mostly from key universities. The comprehensive evaluation of teachers is medium, the distribution of learning burden is polarized, the mastery of professional knowledge is high, and it is very planned and can be

implemented hard. Obvious tendency, mostly from independent colleges, the evaluation of teachers is low, the learning burden is medium or small, the mastery of professional knowledge is medium or low, and there is certain planning and implementation.

3 Results and analysis

In order to explore the influencing factors, this paper establishes a regression analysis based on LASSO logistic, avoiding the problem of more independent variables and discrete values, and uses LASSO regression to constrain the linear model complexity by λ . In contrast, class B is the student who meets the regression criteria. The assigned value is 1; the remaining students are deemed to have not reached the regression criteria, and the assignment value is 0. Therefore, the student category is regarded as the two-category variable and is used as the dependent variable. The observed variables of the "four regressions" are used as independent variables to examine the observed variables. The extent to which students have an impact on the regression criteria.

The post-constrained loss function using λ versus linear model can be expressed as follows:

$$J(\theta) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^m (h_{\theta}(x^{(i)}) - y^{(i)})^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^n |\theta_j|$$

$$\min J(\theta_0, \theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n)$$

The model is fitted using the G language glmnet package. The fitting parameters of each model are shown in Table 3-1. Each row represents a model with a specific lambda value, Df is the degree of freedom, and %Dev represents the proportion of the residual explained by the model. In the model of the model, R² of the model fit is between 0 and 1. The closer to 1, the better the model is. Lambda is the corresponding lambda value of each model.

Table 3-1. Model fitting parameters table

	Df	%Dev	λ
1	0	6.35E-15	2.04E-01
2	5	1.88E-01	1.39E-01
3	6	3.49E-01	9.46E-02
4	9	4.70E-01	6.45E-02
5	13	6.39E-01	2.99E-02
6	15	7.09E-01	2.04E-02
7	18	7.66E-01	1.39E-02
8	19	8.49E-01	6.45E-03
9	19	9.01E-01	2.99E-03
10	21	9.51E-01	9.46E-04
11	21	9.93E-01	9.46E-05
12	22	9.98E-01	2.04E-05

As shown in Table 3-1, as λ becomes smaller, more and more independent variables participate in the model fitting, and %Dev is also getting larger and larger, but it is impossible to determine the exact value of λ taking 9 to 12 lines. To further determine the value. In this paper, we use the model evaluation index AUC (Area under curve) for the two-category model to avoid converting the prediction probability into a category, using cross-validation to output the value of the model AUC under different λ , and using the R language to output the best value of λ . 0.00195, output LASSO-based logistic regression model under this parameter value, the coefficient is shown in Table 3-2.

Table3-2. Regression model coefficient table

Variable	coefficient	Variable	coefficient
C	-10.685	V12	1.883
V1	-2.881	V13	1.663
V2	-1.674	V14	1.610
V3	-2.603	V15	0.950
V4	.	V16	0.847
V5	-0.571	V17	1.256
V6	-1.521	V18	0.625
V7	-0.938	V19	0.311
V8	-0.879	V20	0.383
V9	-0.249	V21	0.338
V10	0.053	V22	-0.070
V11	1.821		

$$p = P(y = 1|x) = \frac{e^{\theta_i x_i + C}}{1 + e^{\theta_i x_i + C}}, \quad i \in E$$

Among them:

$$C = -10.685, \theta_1 = -2.881, \theta_2 = -1.674, \theta_3 = -2.603, \theta_4 = 0, \theta_5 = -0.571, \\ \theta_6 = -1.521, \theta_7 = -0.938, \theta_8 = -0.879, \theta_9 = -0.249, \theta_{10} = 0.053, \\ \theta_{11} = 1.821, \theta_{12} = 1.883, \theta_{13} = 1.663, \theta_{14} = 1.610, \theta_{15} = 0.950, \\ \theta_{16} = 0.847, \theta_{17} = 1.256, \theta_{18} = 0.625, \theta_{19} = 0.311, \theta_{20} = 0.383, \\ \theta_{21} = 0.338, \theta_{22} = -0.070$$

The AUC parameter estimation and confidence interval for this model are shown in Table 3-3. The AUC is approximately 1, and the model fit is very effective.

Table 3-3. AUC confidence intervals

Asymptotic 95% confidence interval		
Lower limit parameter estimation upper limit	Lower limit parameter estimation upper limit	Lower limit parameter estimation upper limit
0.993	0.994	0.998

It can be known from the model coefficients that the factors with strong influence are V1, V2, V3, V6 belonging to "return to common sense," and V11, V12, V13, V14 belonging to "return to the initial heart," that is, defining the regression criteria. After the students, the students' requirements for their own achievements, as well as the amount of reading, the breadth of reading and the burden of learning, have the strongest impact on the students' return. In addition, the four factors of "returning to the score" have a strong influence on whether students can return.

4 Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1 Guide students to return to common sense

Guiding students to return to common sense should be improved from the following aspects: Firstly, enhance the awareness of crisis: colleges and universities should convey the importance of learning and the practicality of

professional knowledge in the future, and establish a fair, reasonable and effective elimination mechanism. Students' crisis awareness enables students to improve their own performance requirements and ease the phenomenon of "zero stress"; secondly, to strengthen the curriculum challenge: the number of courses focusing on cultivating low-level cognitive ability is much more focused on improving high-level cognitive ability. The challenging courses and courses rarely involve challenging topics. It is the main manifestation of the low challenge of university courses in China. For this reason, colleges should adopt small classes to emphasize the cultivation of innovative ability, courage and challenge spirit. Thirdly, organize reading activities and create good reading atmosphere: create a good reading atmosphere by holding topical sharing sessions, topic essays and other reading activities, so that students can broaden their reading breadth and depth in the process of participating in activities; Fourthly, help students to enhance their research intentions and enhance their innovative practice ability: strengthen Student and teacher communication mechanism, allowing students to have channels and the opportunity to find partners and mentors, but also to ensure that mentors can find which is committed to research students, while focusing on innovation and the cultivation of students' self.

4.2 Guide teachers to return to the point

To guide teachers to return to their duty, we should firstly guide teachers to pay attention to theory and practice in teaching. For example, teachers should make full use of the Internet to collect and update the latest information resources before class, and combine theoretical knowledge with real life with specific examples and cases; The teacher should appropriately arrange extracurricular practice, for example, analyze the content of the recent use of certain events. Secondly, guide the teacher to enhance the mental outlook. Teachers should enhance the mental outlook from both internal and external aspects. The external includes the teacher's words and deeds, instruments Intrinsic mainly refers to the teacher's moral character, spiritual realm, and academic ability. The teacher's moral character is extravagant into daily behaviors, which can be visualized and imitated. Therefore, teachers should strictly follow themselves. The moral character is examined many times, and the moral defects are improved by the principle of change, no increase, and at the same time, in addition to work, we must constantly learn and improve our spiritual realm and knowledge. Finally, we should improve the communication between teachers and students after class. Exchange with each other. In order to promote the exchange of teachers and students, the school must pass relevant courses and organize studies. At the same time, the teaching and psychological lectures convey the theory of after-school communication to teachers and students, so that both parties can establish the awareness of active communication. In addition, it is necessary to build communication platforms such as WeChat group and QQ group to avoid the phenomenon that students have no way to ask for advice after class.

4.3 Helping colleges return to their hearts

Helping colleges and universities return to the beginning should improve from the following four aspects: Firstly, build a new academic evaluation system: Colleges and universities should build a balanced and high-standard academic evaluation system that pays attention to students' learning process and results, and raises the minimum compliance index. Classmates shall be punished for punishment and repetition; Secondly, create a good university culture atmosphere: ① Improve the rules and regulations. Establish reasonable and effective rewards and punishments and incentives, reward and punish according to the judgment of students' moral character; ② build a warm and harmonious material environment; ③ develop a rich campus cultural activities; ④ is to establish a noble core spirit of the campus; Thirdly, expand the scope of students' self-selected courses: through the sharing of resources such as teacher resources, quality curriculum resources and online curriculum resources, to open the boundaries of majors, minors, and double degrees, and improve students' self-selection The fourth is to strengthen the ideological and political education reform and innovation: ① set up an excellent group of outstanding ideological and political education teachers; ② innovative ideological and political education forms, enrich the content of ideological and political education.

4.4 Helping education return to dreams

Helping education return to the dream. First of all, we must improve reading interest and build a demand-oriented library: the education department can invite relevant experts to open general courses such as book introduction, reading introduction, and masterpiece reading in the form of online courses, as part of the elective courses of various universities. At the same time, increase the investment in college libraries, such as based on students' digital reading habits, promote the ability of mobile reading services in colleges and universities to meet the needs of college students' personalized digital reading. Secondly, use teaching equipment to stimulate interest and improve efficiency: rational use of multimedia Teaching equipment can stimulate interest in learning and keep it through the teaching activities. Therefore, for the general teaching equipment with long-term use significance, the colleges and universities will be updated in time to improve the learning experience and thus improve the learning efficiency. For the specificity, Update and replace fast equipment, such as: all kinds of experimental equipment, adopt the mode of joint laboratories of various universities, let high-end equipment enter the campus. Finally, we should conduct joint training of schools and enterprises to understand the needs of social talents: local education departments should serve as a bridge, depending on the local area. The needs of sub-enterprises are in contact with different levels of colleges and universities. According to the requirements put forward by enterprises, the school aims to cultivate professional talents for enterprises, adhering to the tenet of "business needs, college training," according to the needs of different levels of talents to set up different levels of courses.

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Notes

♠ Chen Baosheng: "Adhere to the basics of promoting the return to build a first-class undergraduate education with Chinese characteristics and world-class level in the new era of national higher education undergraduate education work conference," June 22, 2018, "Chinese Education newspaper of the first.

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